

TECHNOLOGIES FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF ACTIVITIES BY DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF EDUCATORS

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Abstract. *This article is intended for educators of the preschool educational organization, and as one of the important factors for reforming the educational system, special attention is paid to improving the creative potential and effectiveness of professional and pedagogical activities of educators and professional competence. In addition to enriching educational and educational activities of advanced educational institutions with effective pedagogical technologies, approaches, the need for high competence of specialists in the field is highlighted.*

Keywords: *professional competence of Educators, creativity, pedagogical potential, professional pedagogical activity, competence, efficiency of activity pedagogical technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2019 No. PQ-4312 "On approval of the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", Cabinet of Ministers No. 391 of May 13, 2019 Resolution No. "On measures to further improve the activities of preschool education organizations" was adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Minister of Preschool Education on May 19, 2020. Ensuring the integration of the preschool education system with science, technology and production spheres, which is defined in the order No. 155 "On approval of work documents of pedagogues of state preschool education organizations", is considered as an urgent problem of today. It shows the growing demands for pedagogical skills and professional abilities of specialists working in the field.

Special attention paid to the field of preschool education in the Republic in recent years and a number of documents adopted in this direction allow to create a regulatory and legal framework for improving the quality and efficiency of education.

From this point of view, one of the main tasks of pedagogues is to improve the content of raising the professional competence of preschool teachers based on the pedagogical approach.

State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age of the Republic of Uzbekistan include high-performance modern education and innovative technologies, changes in the field of education, preschool education is the lowest link of the continuous education system. starting from the system, raising a healthy and well-rounded child personality and preparing him for school, healthy gene pool and mature personnel are indicated as extremely important tasks.

Today, one of the original goals of the efforts to develop the education sector in our country is to have intellectual potential, to think independently, to find the necessary information independently and to extract the necessary information from them based on analysis, to communicate with everyone, to use the acquired knowledge in their personal and professional

needs. A lot of attention is paid to the issues of educating young people who can do it. In order to develop such feelings, it is necessary to prepare a person starting from pre-school educational organizations, i.e. logical thinking exercises, to teach the first lessons of foreign languages, at the same time, to develop their creative imagination and to form professional competencies in modern technologies.

In order to solve these tasks, it is necessary to prepare the future educators in the process of learning educational subjects in such a way that they can use them in their life needs, along with acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications. For this, it is necessary to organize the teaching process based on a competent approach. Education based on a competent approach is an education aimed at forming the competencies of practical application of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in their personal, professional and social activities.

II. MAIN PART.

Education based on a competent approach enables educators to have independent thinking, active citizenship, initiative, the ability to attract others with their own point of view, the ability to rationally use communicative communication technologies in their activities, to consciously complete their work. It builds skills such as critical thinking.

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and ownership of a plan of action in complex processes.

"Competence" (eng. "competency" - "ability") - the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional qualifications, skill and talent.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

- in complex processes;
- performing unclear tasks;
- using conflicting information;
- being able to have an action plan in an unexpected situation.

Specialist with professional competence:

- constantly enriches his knowledge;
- learns new information;
- deeply understands the requirements of the era;
- seeks new knowledge;
- processes them and uses them effectively in his practical work

Below, the essence of the qualities reflected on the basis of professional competence will be briefly explained.

1. Social competence - the ability to show activity in social relations, the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

2. Special competence - preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activity, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of BKM, based on this competence psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence noticeable. They contain the following content:

psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in time;

methodical competence - methodically rational organization of the pedagogical process, correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activities, ability to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, ability to use methods effectively, successful use of tools;

informational competence - searching, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and using them purposefully, appropriately, effectively;

creative competence - a critical and creative approach to pedagogical activities, the ability to demonstrate one's own creative skills;

innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and successfully implementing them into practice;

communicative competence - the ability to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them;

personal competence - consistently achieving professional growth, to increase the level of qualification, to demonstrate one's internal capabilities in professional activity;

technological competence - assimilation of advanced technologies that enrich professional and pedagogical BKM, ability to use modern tools, techniques and technologies;

extreme competence - the ability to make rational decisions and act correctly in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failure), when pedagogical disputes arise.

Work on oneself and self-development are important in gaining professional competence of an educator. Self-development tasks are determined through self-analysis and self-assessment.

Working on oneself is the organization of purposeful, consistent, systematic actions by a person or specialist in order to develop oneself socially and professionally, to achieve perfection.

Self-analysis is the study of the nature of the practical actions organized by the pedagogue in professional activity.

Self-assessment is a person's assessment of himself through self-analysis.

CONCLUSION

Technical and human resources that determine the tasks of developing pedagogical skills of employees of preschool educational organizations in the world education system, diversifying educational services, introducing quality management, mutual integration of pedagogical technology and educational strategies, optimizing educational forms and their A systematic

method of creating, applying and defining "whole" processes of teaching and learning, taking into account their interaction, was specially recognized by UNESCO.

One of the main goals of the efforts to develop the education sector in our country is to have intellectual potential, think independently, find the necessary information independently and extract the necessary ones based on analysis, communicate with everyone, apply the acquired knowledge to personal and professional needs. great attention is paid to the issues of educating young people. In order to develop such feelings, it is necessary to prepare a person from pre-school educational institutions, i.e. logical reasoning exercises, to teach the first lessons of foreign languages, at the same time, to develop their pedagogical imagination and to form professional competencies in modern technologies.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to apply it in one's work.

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